

Beyond Simple Nostalgia

Nostalgic Design on the Stage of Modern Chinese Drama

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Abstract: Nostalgic design, which was the design related to nostalgia, became more and more popular in China, especially in Chinese theatre, since 1990s. Somehow, design studies seemed indifferent to this important phenomenon. In order to explore the nostalgic design in Chinese theatre in systemic and comprehensive ways, the paper developed a methodology called scenography semiotics, which derived from theatre semiotics and covered all stage design elements during theatre communications. Applying the methodology to a representative modern Chinese drama, *Boundless Love*, the paper revealed that the nostalgic design did not mechanically copy the past; on the contrary, by adapting various kinds of traditional Chinese art, including traditional Chinese painting, poetry and opera, it artistically presented an integral traditional Chinese aesthetic and utopian space. Confronting the audience with such a space in theatrical ways, the nostalgic design effectively bridged the past and the present, and aroused critical reflections on the present.

Key words: *Nostalgia, nostalgic design, stage design, modern Chinese drama.*

1. Introduction

Nostalgia is a “wistful or excessively sentimental yearning for return to or of some past period or irrecoverable condition”.[1] It is a universal human emotion which has been widely shared by many cultures. In Chinese culture, this kind of emotion is named as *huai jiu*, which means missing the past. The relationship between nostalgia and design is close. Searching key words “nostalgic design” by Google, the researcher find more than two million results on the internet. There is even a design company called NostalgiaDesigns.[2] Although the term “nostalgic design” has already been widely used, surprisingly it has not been academically defined yet. In order to clarify the term, it was tentatively defined as “design related to nostalgia, or design related to the yearning for the past” in this research.

It was true that many nostalgic designs were just some replicas of “old things” which met people’s longing for the past; however, to some Chinese stage designers, nostalgic design was a strategy to facilitate reflection on the present. This design strategy had become more and more noticeable in China since the 1990s, especially in Chinese “new historical dramas”.[3] These dramas were so popular that in 1990s and 2000s they flourished in almost all media, such as theatre, TV, movie, literature, etc. As academic responses, sociology and theatre studies paid great attention to nostalgia and published abundant works, such as *Imagined Nostalgia* by Dai and *The Contemporary Chinese Historical Drama*, by Wagner, etc.[4] In contrast to the attention from other academic fields, design studies seemed indifferent to the issue. As a matter of fact, in these dramas, nostalgic design was not a simple design strategy which merely copied the past; on the contrary, it showed a great

complexity and criticality. Among these cases, *Boundless Love*, which was a modern Chinese drama staged in 2000, drew the researcher's attention. The multilayer and multi-purpose nostalgic design strategy would contribute to the research on design and nostalgia.

Boundless Love was performed in a proscenium theatre in Beijing by Beijing people's Art Theatre in 2000. The box office of the drama was so successful that it earned one million RMB (about 0.15 million USD) within a week.[5] The drama depicted the rise and fall of Chinese dramatist Li Yu and his attitude towards life in the 17th century.[6] The stage photos showed that the stage design was not realistic (Fig.1, 2). Although the dramatic event in the second act was supposed to happen in a boat on the river, there was no sign of boat or river on the stage at all. On the contrary, the stage was so empty that only one backdrop, one screen and several stools appeared in the stage space. Besides the scenic background, some actresses' costumes were also so special that they reminded the audience of traditional Chinese opera, a traditional genre of Chinese theatre originating in 12th century.[7] All the unusual phenomena actually suggested a complicated nostalgic design approach which had not been fully understood by design studies.

The objective of the paper was to reveal that the stage design of *Boundless Love* created a nostalgic design approach which was not a simple approach to miss the past but a critical approach to contemplate on the present. To be specific, the paper would argue that by adapting various kinds of traditional Chinese art, including traditional Chinese painting, poetry and opera, the nostalgic design artistically presented an integral traditional Chinese aesthetic and utopian space. By confronting the audience today with such a space, the nostalgic design intended to effectively bridge the past and the present, and arouse critical reflections on the present.

Fig.1 Second act of *Boundless Love*

Fig.2 Third act of *Boundless Love*

2. Methodology (Scenography Semiotics)

For the sake of systemic and comprehensive stage design studies, the paper applied a methodology called scenography semiotics (Fig.3).[8] The methodology was adapted from theatre semiotics and covered all the elements related to stage design during theatre communications. It was not a mechanical way to analyze the surface of stage; on the contrary, it provided an insightful way to discern the hidden parts of stage.

Fig.3 Scenography semiotics frame

It was necessary to understand semiotics first before introducing scenography semiotics. Semiotics was the study of signs: words and images, in which a meaning was relayed by a corresponding outward manifestation.[9] Saussure defined the sign as having two parts: the signifier, which was the material phenomenon we were able to perceive, and the signified, which was the concept evoked by the signifier.[10] Prague School established the principle that everything within the theatrical frame was a sign.[11] Scenography semiotics was the application of semiotics to stage design as a sign system. It covered the whole process of theatre communication, from scenography production to feedback. It consisted of three parts, which were categorized by different stages of theatre communication. The first category was about the context of scenography, which could be thought as a precondition before the performance. It included four aspects: “social context”, which was the political, economic and cultural condition of a society, “theatre concept”, which was the main understanding of theatre, “director and designer’s conception”, which was director and designer’s understandings of theatre, and “dramatic text”, which was the script. The second category was about the sign systems during performance. Due to the attribute of stage signs, it included three sub-categories: “signifier”, “signified” and “signifier-signified relationship”. The “signifier” sub-category consisted of two aspects: “elements”, which included theatre type, scenic background, properties, body, costume and lighting, and “arrangement”, which included the performance area, time-space change mode and stage-audience relationship. The “signified” sub-category consisted of three aspects: “representative layer”, which represented fictional environment, “expressive layer” which represented aesthetics, atmosphere, mood and style, and “symbolic layer”, which represented symbolic meanings. “Signifier-signified relationship” sub-category focused on the relationship between the signifier and signified. The third category was about the response to the scenography after performance. It consisted of “audience’s responses”, which were comments from audience and box office, and “critics’ comments”, which were criticisms. The multi-layer frame of scenography semiotics suggested its capability to reveal some “invisible” information, relationship and meanings on stage.

It should be noted that although the methodology seemed to disappear in the writing of the research, it actually guided the whole research. Since the paper regarded it as an insightful way to analyze stage design rather than a mechanical way to present the results of analysis, the clumsy frame of the methodology dissolved in the writing. However, each element of the methodology frame, such as director and designer's conception, scenic background, property, body, costume, stage-audience relationship, symbolic meaning, signifier-signified relationship, audience reaction, etc., still existed in the writing. Moreover, the elements of stage design were carefully grouped and rearranged in the writing so that the research topic could be clearly supported.

3. Nostalgic Sign systems in *Boundless Love*

3.1. Nostalgic Design and Traditional Chinese Painting

Fig.4 *Night Revels of Han Xizai*, painted in Five Dynasties and Ten Kingdoms (907-979)

By applying scenography semiotics to the stage of *Boundless Love*, it could be found that the nostalgic design adapted various kinds of traditional Chinese arts. Traditional Chinese painting, for instance, was obviously borrowed by the design. The paintings of peonies on screen and mountains on backdrop were segments deriving from two traditional Chinese paintings in Song Dynasty (960-1279) (Fig.1).[Yi, personal communication] Besides, a women band on backdrop (Fig.2) was a segment deriving from the Chinese painting *Night Revels of Han Xizai*, painted in Five Dynasties and Ten Kingdoms (907-979) (Fig.4). Borrowing the forms of Chinese painting, the design actually borrowed the aesthetics and cultural meanings within the works as well. Traditional Chinese painting was famous for its characteristic of *xieyi*, or essentialism, which depicted the “essence rather than the appearance of things”.[12] Not only exclusive to Chinese paintings, *xieyi* was also considered as the main aesthetics of overall tradition Chinese arts, such as Chinese opera.[13] Merely by “exhibiting” Chinese painting, the representative agent of *xieyi*, the unique traditional Chinese aesthetics could be visually perceived at first sight. From the vague mountains and clouds with spirits instead of details, the audience could easily grasp the Chinese aesthetics without any textual explanations. It was a direct and effective method to reveal traditional Chinese aesthetics. Moreover, Chinese painting was not only an aesthetic production but also a cultural production combining history, insight and emotion. From this point of view, every Chinese painting in the drama was born to go beyond a signifier which merely represented fictional environments of the play; in fact, they should also represent certain atmospheres, moods and meanings. The designer clearly grasped this view and made full use of it. The painting, *Night Revels of Han Xizai*, was such a case (Fig.4). It was a famous Chinese painting depicting an official's indulgent nightlife. In the painting, the official was so frustrated that he reveled in wine, music and dance at night.[14] The third act borrowed the story of the painting to express the hero's frustration in a cultural way. Only by understanding the culture of the painting, the inner frustration of the hero, which was in the disguise of outward revel, could be fully grasped. Since the painting also had allegoric meanings, citing the painting rendered the hero and his life in the drama

allegoric. In this way, the play no more depicted a life of an individual living in the past, but revealed general living conditions of all human beings at the present. As a result, the meaning and depth of the drama were greatly extended by the design. Thus, it could be concluded that the nostalgic design did not simply cite Chinese paintings for “exhibiting” antiques; instead, it intellectually revived the aesthetics and meanings within these works.

Fig.5 Utopian scenery in the fourth act

Fig.6 Costume and prop of traditional Chinese opera

3.2. Nostalgic Design and Traditional Chinese Poetry

Besides traditional Chinese paintings, the nostalgic design also adapted the works of traditional Chinese poetry to create a traditional utopian and aesthetic space. The stage design of the fourth act (Fig.5), which mainly consisted of some yellow flowers and the backdrop with ink painting mountains, reminded the audience of a famous traditional Chinese idyllic poem, *Drinking*. The poem was written by Chinese literatus Tao Yuanming in Jin Dynasty (265-420), which was more than 1,500 years ago. The poem depicted the literatus’ reclusive life and his thinking about the reclusion and the world. The poem wrote,

Within the world of men I make my home,
 Yet din of house and carriage there is none;
 You ask me how this quiet is achieved—
 With thoughts remote the place appears alone.
 While picking asters neath the Eastern fence,
 My gaze upon the Southern mountain rests;
 The mountain views are good by day or night,
 The birds come flying homeward to their nests.
 A truth in this reflection lies concealed,
 But I forget how it may be revealed.[15]

From the lines, the literatus expressed that he pursued an idyllic life which was close to nature and far from secularity. To him, the great spiritual satisfaction was from his appreciation of the nature rather than the luxurious material life. His poem constructed a Chinese utopia and this utopia was carried on from generation to generation. Many great Chinese literati in Chinese history acclaimed this utopia and regarded it as an alternative to the unpleasant reality.[16] In *Boundless Love*, the stage designer once again inherited this

tradition and made use of the ancient utopia. By visualizing the most famous idyllic lines “While picking asters neath the Eastern fence, my gaze upon the Southern mountain rests”, the nostalgic design aroused the ancient but lasting Chinese utopia in the stage space. Not only did the nostalgic design create the stage form deriving from the poem, but also created the stage style which followed the essence of the poem. Like the poem, the stage design was austere, concise and idyllic. Only the most idyllic and suggestive elements, such as yellow flowers and ink painting mountains, were placed on the empty stage. As a result, “less is more” effect was achieved. The utopia behind the lines had been tacitly and poetically revealed by the nostalgic design.

3.3. Nostalgic Design and Traditional Chinese Opera

In addition to some non-theatrical arts, the nostalgic design also adapted a traditional genre of theatre, traditional Chinese opera, to create a traditional aesthetic space. *Boundless Love* was a modern Chinese drama; however, it undoubtedly assimilated its counterpart and “rival”, traditional Chinese opera. It was known that traditional Chinese opera was a genre of theatre originated in China as early as 12th century. It was the genre which combined singing, speaking, acting, and acrobatics.[17] However, at the turn of 20th century, it was viewed as too constraining for expressing the concerns of an increasingly modern world. Due to this reason, modern Chinese drama (also known as spoken drama, or *Huaju*) was invented by Chinese students abroad at the beginning of 20th century. In contrast to traditional Chinese opera, modern Chinese drama imitated Western dramatic conventions.[18] Consisting mostly of speaking and acting, modern Chinese drama emerged as a rival to traditional Chinese opera and soon became one of the most primary types of dramas in China. However, in 1950s, the sinicization of modern Chinese drama started by learning from traditional Chinese opera. Fifty years later, at the very end of 20th century, *Boundless Love* once again “betrayed” the initial purpose of modern Chinese drama; on the contrary, it allied with the rival, traditional Chinese opera, in more various ways. At this time, not only the forms of traditional Chinese opera, but also the essence of traditional Chinese opera was adopted by *Boundless Love*.

The adaptation of traditional Chinese opera was mainly achieved by two methods: play-within-the-play and assimilation. The first method was to use play-within-the-play structure to incite traditional Chinese opera intactly. Play-within-the-play refers to “a play that is presented by characters who are already in a play.”[19] Many famous plays contain such plays-within-plays, such as Chekhov’s *The Seagull*, Shakespeare’s *A Midsummer Night’s Dream*, and Lai Chuansheng’s *Secret Love for the Peach Blossom Spring*, etc.[20] In *Boundless Love*, the dramatist devised a play-within-the-play structure to seamlessly connect two distinct genres, modern Chinese drama and traditional Chinese opera. To be specific, the dramatist devised some deliberate plots to enable the fictional heroine, who was a traditional Chinese opera actress, to perform the authentic opera directly. By this method, the original props, costumes and performances of traditional Chinese opera accessed to modern Chinese drama directly. For example, in the fifth act, the actress, who used to learn traditional Chinese opera in 1980s, performed with costumes with long sleeves, headdress with luxurious decorations, and makeup with conventional patterns (Fig.6).[21] Besides, some symbolic props of traditional Chinese opera were also kept on the stage exactly. For instance, the chair covered by the patterned silk, which was an essential convention of traditional Chinese opera, was placed around the actress. At a surface level, all these noticeable features of traditional Chinese opera engendered a genuine traditional aesthetic space.

Different from the first method, which merely borrowed the form of traditional Chinese opera, the second method assimilated both the form and aesthetics of traditional Chinese opera. The director of *Boundless Love*, Lin Zhaohua, had paid attention to traditional Chinese opera since 1980s. He admired the aesthetic principle and free artistic spirit of traditional Chinese opera.[22] He claimed that not only the surface, but the aesthetics of traditional Chinese opera should be assimilated by modern Chinese drama.[23] By studying and practising, he concluded that the aesthetic principle of traditional Chinese opera was void.[24] To him, it was because of the void that a limited stage could represent unlimited space and got great freedom.[25]

Fig.7 Baziyi paradigm

Fig.8 Layout of the second act

According to his reflection on the aesthetics of traditional Chinese opera, Director Lin and his designer created a void stage in *Boundless Love*. To be specific, the stage was void in two senses: empty space and empty signified. First, at a surface level, the stage was an empty space. Taking the second act as an example (Fig. 1), although the plot was supposed to happen in a grand boat on a river, director and designer did not make any effort to visualize the boat or even the frame of the boat on the stage. In fact, the stage was so void that only five props, which were one armchair, two stools, one screen and one backdrop, were placed on the illuminated area of the stage. Both the minimized props and their layout suggested a close relation with traditional Chinese opera. It was known that the key stage structure of traditional Chinese opera was minimized and concluded as “one table and two chairs, curtain and backdrop”.[26] It meant that as few as three props were enough for a formal performance of traditional Chinese opera. In addition, the way to arrange these props was constrained to some conventional paradigms. *Baziyi* paradigm, for example, was a pattern which placed a table in the middle and aligned two chairs symmetrically around the table (Fig.7).[27] Designer Yi Liming claimed that table and chairs should not be considered as a part of stage design but the very nature and essence of traditional Chinese opera.[Yi, personal communication] Due to these reasons, the stage design followed both the minimum principle and the paradigm principle. Comparing the layout of the second act with *Baziyi* paradigm, the audience could find great similarities (Fig.8). Despite a few minor differences, the core elements of the paradigm, chairs or stools, were faithfully kept on the stage. The layout of the chair, stools and screen (a kind of backdrop) also obeyed the paradigm firmly. By adapting the paradigm to a minor degree, the design preserved the aesthetics of traditional Chinese opera, void of the space.

Second, at a semantic level, it was a space with empty signified. Realistic stage represented a specific physical location in which plots happened. Because of this, scenic background had to be changed when the location of the plots changed. However, in traditional Chinese opera, the stage was a neutral space, which was suitable for all the different scenes in one drama. This kind of stage space didn't depict the environments of any different scenes in details; instead, it was a space with empty signified unless the actors and events semanticized the meaning into it. This theatrical technique, which had also been the essence of traditional Chinese opera, was grasped by the design of *Boundless Love*. Although the backdrop depicted some vague mountains with clouds, which derived from a Chinese painting named *Spectacles of Xiaoxiang* in Song Dynasty (960-1279), it remained the same no matter how the fictional location changed.[28] The stage space seemed not to assign to a fixed location but exist as an empty signifier which awaited to be semanticized by performance and lines. As a result, the stage achieved another kind of aesthetics of traditional Chinese opera, void of the signified. Thus, by creating a void space in both spatial and semantic senses, the nostalgic design assimilated both the form and aesthetics of traditional Chinese opera.

4. Discussions

4.1. Nostalgic Design and the Integral Traditional Aesthetic and Utopian Space

Borrowing, adapting and assimilating various traditional Chinese arts, the nostalgic design actually tried to create an integral rather than a discrete traditional Chinese aesthetic and utopian space. The former analysis had revealed that the whole stage was not a replica of a certain place in a certain period, but a collage of traditional Chinese arts from very different historical periods. In other words, the stage did not mean to signify an explicit physical location; in fact, the stage design had actually gone beyond the functional level and towards the aesthetic level. Like Designer Yi said, to him, *Boundless Love* was an aesthetic drama, and it was the aesthetic aspects that guided the stage design.[Yi, personal communication] His words revealed that what he valued was not the works of art themselves but the integral Chinese aesthetics within them. He further explicated that *Boundless Love* was a "literati theatre", which was a coinage derived from literati painting (a genre of traditional Chinese painting).[Yi, personal communication] Like the literati painting, which appreciated the integral aesthetics of poem, calligraphy, painting and seal, "literati theatre" valued an integral and high aesthetics from various forms of arts.[29] He concluded this integral aesthetics as *Shiqing Huayi*, which meant a quality suggestive of poem or painting. The name of the aesthetics had self-evidently revealed its close relation with traditional Chinese paintings and poetry. Since the appreciation of this quality rested in the nation's collective consciousness and unconsciousness, citing the masterpieces of traditional arts might be the most tacit and effective way to arouse the integral traditional aesthetics. It might be the main reason why designer borrowed so many works of traditional Chinese art to revive the traditional Chinese aesthetics and utopia in stage space.

Besides creating an integral aesthetic and utopian space on stage, the designer also impressively confronted the stage space with the audience by innovative theatrical skills. The stage-audience relationship was a very unique characteristic of theatre. The concept referred to a placement of the stage and audience, which could influence both transmission and reception of the performance.[30] It was so important that little theatre and avant-garde theatre often devoted themselves to change, improve or even revolt the relationship. In *Boundless Love*, designer did not waste the opportunity to improve the relationship by traditional Chinese aesthetics. This time,

he chose water as the media to fulfill his experiment. Water, in Chinese aesthetics, had its very specific beauty and poetic romance. Both traditional Chinese painting and poetry had passion and tradition to depict water in artistic ways. Following the tradition, the designer considered the water in *Boundless Love* as poetic instead of physical. He was eager to extend the aesthetic and utopian atmosphere on stage to the whole theatre, no matter performance area or spectator area. Finally, he succeeded by hiding a big tank of water beneath the forestage (Fig.9). As a result, when lighting focused on the water, the reflections of the lighting and ripples shimmered inside the theatre hall (Fig.10). It seemed to extend the aesthetic stage space to the whole theatre space. The distance between spectator and performer, no matter in physical or psychological sense, was largely shortened. The “wall” between the performance area and spectator dissolved in the poetic Chinese aesthetic atmosphere. Thus, the audience was exposed to traditional Chinese aesthetics and utopia more directly. Thus, by citing and innovating, the nostalgic design transformed physical stage space into an integral Chinese aesthetic space and confronted the audience with the space.

Fig.9 A tank of water beneath the forestage

Fig.10 Shimmering reflections of lighting and ripples

4.2. Nostalgic Design and Critical Reflections on the Present

The nostalgic design confronted the audience today with traditional Chinese aesthetics and utopia; however, the main purpose of doing so was not to miss the past, but to contemplate the present. The idea was supported by the designer of *Boundless Love*, Yi Liming, who claimed that theatre should facilitate audience’s reflection on the status quo. [Yi, personal communication]

In nature, *Boundless Love* followed a very Chinese approach of criticism, which hardly criticized the present directly but took history as a mirror. As early as one thousand years ago, Chinese intellectual believed that rereading the nation’s past helped to examine the current situation and revitalize the lost merits.[31] *Boundless Love* was written and directed under this traditional belief. It belonged to a category of dramas called “new historical dramas”, which was invented by Chinese intellectual in China in 1920s.[32] This category of dramas employed historical materials which were allegorically relevant to the contemporary social situation.[33] The purpose of the category was to reflect on the present rather than return to the past. Taking *Boundless Love* as an example, the drama was about a Chinese dramatist Li Yu, who lived in the 17th Century. Although living in a pre-consumerist society three hundred years ago, the hero had a “modern” character from which the audience

today could see their projections.[34] On one hand he disputed money, but on the other hand he could not live without it; on one hand he disliked politics, but on the other hand he wanted to take part in it. His contradictory attitude about money, career, life and love was controversial but educative to the audience today. He was like a mirror, in which the audience today could introspect themselves and contemplate the society today. It was the real and underlying purpose of the drama.

Yi agreed that the purpose of the drama was also the purpose of stage design.[Yi, personal communication] He said, “No matter the stage is classic, modern or absurd, its purpose is to communicate with the contemporary people better.... In nature, stage design is to communicate with the contemporary people.”[Yi, personal communication] He further asserted that expressing the purpose of drama to the audience at first sight was his aim. [Yi, personal communication] In other words, he thought the purpose of drama should be perceived in a visual and effective way. With this belief, he refused to adopt a clumsy physical stage; instead, he abstracted an integral spirit of the past by adapting masterpieces of traditional Chinese painting, poetry and opera. The *xieyi*, utopia and void which were abstracted from the works of traditional arts greatly contrasted to the aesthetics of consumer society today, which preferred sensory overload, fetish and surplus.[35] Moreover, the Chinese aesthetics, *Shiqing Huayi*, also represented a spiritual standard which was beyond the material and mundane life.[36] In traditional Chinese culture, *Shiqing Huayi* was a symbol of good morality, broad knowledge and deep insight.[37] It was pursued by ancient Chinese literati, who were key contributors to classic Chinese culture.[38] Its spiritual content contrasted with the fetishism and consumerism of the contemporary Chinese society greatly. The contrast reminded the audience of valuable Chinese identity and culture in history and pushed the audience to reflect on their status quo. In this way, the past effectively functioned as a mirror of today and stimulated audience’s contemplation both emotionally and intellectually. After the performance, some audience commented that the drama was like a cup of Chinese tea, which helped them to forget the din of city and enjoy the peace from heart.[39] The comments had endorsed that the designer’s strategy worked. Creating and radiating such a traditional space on a spiritual level, the design bridged the conversation between the past and the present and facilitated thinking. The purpose of the drama, thus, was revealed and the task of nostalgic design was fulfilled.

Due to these reasons, it could be concluded that the nostalgic design revived traditional Chinese aesthetics and utopia to reflect on the present rather than to miss the past.

5. Conclusions and Further Applications

In conclusion, by applying the methodology scenography semiotics to the representative modern Chinese drama, *Boundless Love*, the paper revealed a complex nostalgic design strategy. The nostalgic design did not mechanically copy the past; on the contrary, by adapting various kinds of traditional Chinese art, including traditional Chinese painting, poetry and opera, it artistically presented an integral traditional Chinese aesthetic and utopian space. Confronting the audience with such a space in an innovative theatrical way, the nostalgic design effectively bridged the past and the present, and aroused critical reflections on the present.

The critical nostalgic design revealed by the research might be enlightening to several kinds of designs and arts,

such as architecture, interior design, exhibition design, stage design and installation art. In many occasions, nostalgic design merely treated the past as decorative signs which created fake spectacles of the past; however, nostalgic design could and should be sharper. The past, which was ancestors' experiences, values and wisdoms, was more than superficial forms to designers. Exploring spirits of the past instead of merely borrowing forms of the past was designers' indispensable mission. Only by achieving the mission, design became an intellectual field which not only met people's desire but also educated and improved people. The strategy that using nostalgic design as social critique to reflect on the contemporary culture had set an example for designers who wished to improve the contemporary nostalgic design.

(Fig.1, 2, 5, 6 are captured from the video clip *Boundless Love*, published by Beijing Culture & Art Audio & Video Press and Lin Zhaohua Theatre Studio. Fig.4 is from Wikipedia. Fig.9, 10 are captured from the video clip *Life Online*, published by Beijing Culture & Art Audio & Video Press and Lin Zhaohua Theatre Studio.)

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